

MODERATING EFFECT OF INFLATION ON FIRM CHARACTERISTICS AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF QUOTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The absence of stringent compliance legislation mandating organizations to engage in corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities often leads many to remain non-committal regarding the impacts of their operations on both people and the environment. Consequently, there is a pressing need for periodic assessments to understand how unique factors related to firms influence their decisions regarding social responsibility. Against this backdrop, this study examines the correlation between the characteristics of industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) Limited from 2010-2022 and their CSR practices, with inflation considered as a moderating variable. The study's population comprises the thirteen industrial goods companies listed on the NGX Limited as of December 31, 2022, and a complete sampling method was employed. A bi-model analysis was adopted for clarity, incorporating pooled OLS and Fixed Effect regression methods. Findings from Model I indicate that profitability, as measured by return on assets, exhibits an insignificant positive association with corporate social responsibility, while the leverage ratio demonstrates a significant negative relationship. Model II reveals that inflation rates have an insignificant negative moderating impact on the relationship between profitability and CSR and an insignificant positive effect on the relationship between leverage and CSR. In light of these results, the study recommends that firms aspiring to be responsible corporate citizens should focus on achieving profitability and avoid excessive indebtedness. This approach allows companies to allocate more resources to address the social needs of their various stakeholders.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Firm Characteristics, Inflation Rates, Leverage ratio, Profitability, Return on Assets.

Introduction

The traditional understanding of corporate firms' roles has been centered around a commercial business paradigm focused on achieving economic profitability and success. However, in recent years, the perception of corporate responsibilities in the broader societal context has evolved due to increasing globalization and pressing ecological concerns. This shift involves redefining firms' obligations to encompass not only financial goals but also societal and environmental responsibilities. Recognizing the significant impact of corporate economic actions on people's lives, a specialized accounting system known as social responsibility accounting (SRA) has

emerged. SRA addresses the measurement, assessment, and summarization of the social costs and benefits associated with a company's activities. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) entails the application of social responsibility accounting within organizations, with an emphasis on public communication through social disclosure, often presented in corporate annual reports (Shabririna & Cahyono, 2023).

Audu *et al.* (2022) contended that the inclination of companies, particularly those engaged in environmentally risky activities, to initiate social programs presents a challenge to the discourse surrounding corporate social responsibility. Akubo *i.* (2018) emphasized that every organization has specific obligations to fulfil to have a positive impact on the local community, the environment, and the overall well-being of the people in its vicinity. Aliyu *et al.* (2021) observed that the expectations from business management extend beyond mere profit maximization, now encompassing considerations for stakeholders. The imperative for companies to take responsibility for environmental welfare and sustainability prompted a shift from the traditional single-bottom-line approach, where economic interests were the sole focus, to the contemporary Triple-bottom-line framework. This framework places the responsibility for societal and environmental well-being squarely on businesses (Santioso & Chandra, 2012).

Supporting the idea of corporate entities embracing social responsibility for the well-being of society and the environment for future generations, the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018) emphasizes the importance of sustainability issues, encompassing the environment, social aspects, occupational health, and community safety. Part E, Principle 26 of the code mandates companies to prioritize these concerns, ensuring both successful long-term business performance and projecting the company as a responsible corporate citizen contributing to economic development. To further underscore the necessity of social responsibility for companies in their interactions with stakeholders, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) introduced ISO 26000 in 2010 (officially ratified in 2017) as a guide for organizations to adopt more socially responsible practices (Mukhtaruddin *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards, established by a global body, serve as benchmarks for publicly reporting on a range of economic, environmental, and social impacts, reflecting global best practices (Aimuyedo *et al.*,

Characteristics of a firm encompass features that fall into categories of uncontrollable, partially controllable, and controllable, specific to that particular firm. These distinct attributes include elements such as firm size, the size of the board of directors, the existence of an audit committee, audit quality,

auditor type, independence of the board and audit committee, and corporate image, among others (Adediran *et al.*, 2019). Uncontrollable characteristics, like company size, structure, and age, are beyond a firm's direct influence. This study specifically focuses on profitability and firm leverage as the considered characteristics. Inflation is defined as the gradual increase in the overall price level of goods and services in an economy, resulting in each unit of currency purchasing fewer goods and services over time. Inflation represents a reduction in the purchasing power of money, reflecting a real value loss in the internal medium of exchange and unit of account within the economy (Ali & Ibrahim, 2018). During periods of inflation, saving is discouraged as the value of saved funds diminishes in comparison to the current situation. A variable is deemed a moderating variable, according to Hair *et al.* (1998), if its impact on the relationship between two or more other variables depends on its level. In this study, inflation is employed as a moderating variable because it is connected to the resources that firms can allocate to societal and environmental concerns (Batsinda & Shukla, 2019).

The manufacturing sector in Nigeria includes industrial goods companies that are engaged in the production of items like cement, paints, chemicals, electric cables, and tires, among other products. Their activities are overseen by the Code of Corporate Governance, with the most recent edition being from 2018. Notably, the industrial goods companies constitute a subsector that has experienced a significant number of delistings from the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Between 2008 and 2021, a total of eighteen (18) industrial companies were removed from the exchange for various reasons (NGX, 2022).

The problem statement for this study arises from identified concerns in the existing literature, highlighting the imperative nature of the current research. Noteworthy issues encompass inappropriate methodology, particularly the absence of studies conducting both autocorrelation and multicollinearity tests to ascertain potential correlation problems within independent variables or among pairs of independent variables. Additionally, recent studies, such as Shabirina and Cahyono (2023), have been criticized for their shorter time frames, deemed insufficient for establishing robust findings and conclusions. Furthermore, there is a noticeable gap in studies exploring the moderating role of a third variable, specifically inflation rates, in the relationship between the variables under investigation.

The overarching aim of this study is to examine how inflation influences the relationship between firm characteristics and corporate social responsibility among industrial goods companies listed in Nigeria. The specific objectives are i) assess the correlation between

profitability and corporate social responsibility in the quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria; ii) examine the link between the firm leverage ratio and corporate social responsibility of industrial goods companies in Nigeria; iii) evaluate the moderating impact of inflation rates on the relationship between profitability and corporate social responsibility in the quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria; and iv) explore the moderating effect of inflation rates on the relationship between leverage ratio and corporate social responsibility among the quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

To address the aforementioned objectives, the following non-directional null hypotheses were formulated for examination. Ho₁: There is no significant association between profitability and the corporate social responsibility of industrial goods companies listed in Nigeria. Ho₂: The leverage ratio does not have a significant correlation with the corporate social responsibility of industrial goods companies listed in Nigeria. Ho₃: The inflation rate does not exert a significant moderating influence on the relationship between profitability and corporate social responsibility among quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Ho₄: The inflation rate does not exert a significant moderating influence on the relationship between the leverage ratio and corporate social responsibility among quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The study encompasses thirteen Nigerian industrial goods companies and spans a duration of thirteen years, from 2010 to 2012

Review of Literature

Firm Characteristics

Zayol *et al.* (2021) characterized firm attributes as the diverse qualities that qualify a firm as an independent entity or a unit responsible for producing goods and services for public consumption. Firm characteristics, also known as corporate attributes, play a role in influencing the extent of a firm's environmental and social responsibility practices. According to Shuaibu (2020), these characteristics are the distinctive features that determine a firm's operational activities and serve as key factors in the firm's financial decision-making. Valipour *et al.* (2012) identified firm characteristics such as operating income, firm size, bargain development, current ratio, quick ratio, and debt ratio. Kogan and Tian (2012) argued that firm characteristics encompass elements like firm size, corporate influence, liquidity, sales development, asset improvement, and turnover rates. Ekpa *et al.* (2019) defined firm characteristics as distinguishing

features among firms. In this study, firm characteristics are delineated as features that set one firm apart from another, specifically represented by profitability, firm size, firm leverage, and firm age.

Profitability and Corporate Social Responsibility

Rohmadini *et al.* (2018) characterized profitability as the aptitude for generating earnings or profits within a specific timeframe. Tan (2022) outlined profitability as an indicator of a company's financial robustness, gauging the capacity of its available assets to generate profits. Astuti (2018) emphasized that a company's profitability plays a pivotal role in enabling management to openly address social responsibility to shareholders. Furthermore, she asserted that higher profitability levels correlate with increased commitments and disclosure of social responsibility by firms. Ibrahim *et al.* (2020) observed that profitability is more accurately elucidated by the concept of returns on assets (ROA), which assesses earnings concerning a firm's total assets. Yuliana *et al.* (2008) contended that mere profit generation does not ensure a company's adherence to sustainability unless it actively responds to the demands of its environment and society. Edicha *et al.* (2021) contended that a company's return on assets (ROA) serves as an indicator of its proficiency in utilizing assets effectively to yield favourable returns. This study defines profitability as the disparity between income generated and expenditures incurred, measuring it as the total profit after tax divided by total assets (ROA).

Leverage Ratio and Corporate Social Responsibility

The ratio of debt to equity used by a company to finance its assets is known as the leverage or gearing ratio. According to Adam (2020), leverage is an investment strategy involving borrowing funds through various financial instruments to enhance the potential returns of an investment. Cui (2020) argues that debt financing compels companies to prioritize the interests of creditors, potentially neglecting other stakeholders. Conversely, a zero-leverage policy relieves firms of financial burdens, allowing them to act more responsibly. Tan (2022) asserts that higher leverage increases the likelihood of violating credit agreements, leading companies to attempt to boost reported profits by cutting costs, including those related to corporate social responsibility. Swandari and Sadikin (2016) emphasize that a company's debt level negatively affects its socially responsible behaviour, as higher debt levels force a focus on managing business risks

rather than engaging in socially responsible activities. This study defines leverage as the borrowed component in a firm's capital structure

Corporate Social Responsibility

Al-Akayleh and Saaydah (2022) highlighted the absence of a universally accepted definition for corporate social responsibility (CSR), emphasizing the proliferation and evolution of its definitions. They explained that CSR encompasses various areas and associated activities, with a primary focus on initiatives directed towards the community and the environment. According to Ezejiofor and Emeneka (2022), the concept of corporate social responsibility is inherently linked to sustainable development, requiring businesses to assume full responsibility for safeguarding the natural environment, the condition of which profoundly influences. The European Union Commission (2002) defined corporate social responsibility as a concept where companies voluntarily incorporate social and environmental considerations into their business operations and interactions with stakeholders. This study defines corporate social responsibility as 'do not eat alone' accounting framework.

Inflation Rate (The Moderating Variable)

Ichado *et al.* (2020) characterized inflation as alterations in the purchasing power of a country's currency. Ali and Ibrahim (2018) delineated inflation as an elevation in the overall price level of goods and services within an economy over a period, resulting in each unit of currency being able to procure a reduced quantity of goods and services. This phenomenon signifies a reduction in the purchasing power of money due to the depreciation of real value within the internal medium of exchange of an economy. In line with Lai's (2013) perspective, a moderator is an independent variable that influences the strength and/or direction of the relationship between another independent variable and a dependent variable. Building upon Kennedy's (2008) assertion, the selection of the independent variable (firm characteristics) should be conducted in a manner that provides clear justifications for highlighting the significance of inflation in its association with corporate social responsibility. This study defines inflation rates as fluctuations in the purchasing power of a national currency.

2.3 Empirical Review

Shabirina and Cahyono (2023) explored the impact of various firm characteristics, including size, profitability, liquidity, leverage, and public ownership, on the disclosure of corporate social

responsibility (CSR). The disclosure of corporate social responsibility was assessed based on the 2016 Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI) Standards Disclosure Index, which is available in the company's annual report. The researchers employed the multiple linear regression method for data analysis, incorporating the coefficient of determination, f-test, and t-test. The findings revealed that firm size and public ownership significantly influence corporate social responsibility, whereas profitability, liquidity, and leverage do not exhibit a significant impact. The study recommended that future research should extend its scope beyond the manufacturing sector and include various industries. Additionally, it suggested extending the research period beyond the three-year duration used in the study for more robust findings. The study emphasized that the inclusion of only 58 companies out of 193 makes it challenging to generalize the findings to the entire manufacturing sector.

Zaman *et al.* (2023) investigated the correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and the Zero Leverage (ZL) policy implemented by companies. Employing panel logistic multivariate regression, the study aimed to assess the socially responsible behaviour of both ZL firms and their leveraged counterparts. The dataset comprised firm-year observations of listed companies in Pakistan spanning from 2009 to 2018, which were further categorized into subsamples representing short-term ZL and long-term ZL firms. The findings revealed a significant and positive relationship between CSR and ZL policies. Notably, financially unconstrained socially responsible firms exhibited a higher likelihood of adopting the ZL policy. The study suggested that utilizing a global dataset could address the data limitations of this research and yield more widely applicable results.

Ezejiolor and Emeneka (2022) investigated the impact of leverage on the sustainability reporting of Oil and Gas firms listed in Nigeria. The researchers utilized secondary data obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the selected firms. Panel Least Square (PLS) regression analysis was employed to analyze extracts from the annual reports. The empirical analysis revealed a significant influence of leverage on social sustainability reporting in Nigeria. As a result of the unfavourable connections between leverage and social responsibility reporting, the study recommended that companies should prioritize gaining a deeper understanding of the importance of robust environmental practices and disclosures. This understanding could contribute to lowering debt costs and enhancing social reporting.

Aimuyedo *et al.* (2022) explored the impact of leverage on sustainability reporting in the Industrial goods sector in Nigeria, considering firm size as a moderating factor. The study aimed to assess the influence of leverage on social responsibility and examine how firm size affects this relationship over 11 years (2009-2019). The study focused on the population of 14 listed industrial firms in Nigeria, excluding 2 companies due to insufficient data, resulting in a sample size of 12 listed companies. Employing an ex-post facto research design, the study utilized panel data from annual and sustainability reports. The analysis, conducted through linear multiple regression and content analysis of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) G4 index, unveiled a statistically significant positive impact of leverage on sustainability reporting. Notably, the study found that the effect of leverage on sustainability reporting was amplified when firm size acted as a moderating variable. The findings suggest that stakeholders should persist in urging organizations to enhance their social and environmental responsibility. Additionally, the study recommended that the Nigerian Group Exchange (NGX) and the government take measures to promote and enforce stricter compliance for improved sustainability disclosures.

Shuaibu (2020) conducted a study to investigate how firm characteristics affect the quality of corporate environmental disclosure among listed cement companies in Nigeria. The data utilized in the research were sourced from the annual reports and accounts of these companies spanning the years 2013 to 2017. Content analysis, employing GRI as a disclosure index, was applied to scrutinize the reports. Additionally, data analysis involved descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression techniques, facilitated by STATA 12.0. The results of the study indicated that firm age, firm size, and leverage significantly influence the quality of corporate environmental disclosure. Notably, the findings suggested that maintaining an optimal debt level and exercising control over firm size are crucial for enhancing the quality of environmental disclosure among listed cement companies in Nigeria. The study offered recommendations, emphasizing the importance of these factors in shaping environmental disclosure practices.

Theoretical Review

Legitimacy Theory

This study is grounded in the Legitimacy Theory formulated by Dowling and Pfeffer in 1975. The theory posits that organizations' policies should align with those of the larger society. Legitimacy, as defined by Dowling and Pfeffer (1975), is the condition where an entity's values

match those of the broader social system it is a part of. Legitimacy, in this context, is a perceived alignment with socially constructed norms, values, beliefs, and definitions, signifying that the entity's actions are deemed desirable, proper, or fitting. A fundamental tenet of the legitimacy theory is that society permits an organization to operate as long as it fulfils societal expectations. The theory's strength lies in its stakeholder-centric approach, harmonizing with the broader Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) perspective. However, a limitation of the legitimacy theory is its emphasis on explaining past actions rather than forecasting future behaviour, which may constrain organizations from seeking proactive strategies. This study discerned that companies exhibit a higher inclination toward engaging in social activities when they generate profits.

Methodology

This study employs an ex-post facto research design due to the exclusively historical nature of the data. This design is deemed appropriate for its high level of verifiability and reliability. The study focuses on a population consisting of thirteen industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) Limited as of December 31, 2022. To ensure comprehensive coverage, the study samples all thirteen companies, as the number of units is manageable. Census sampling is employed, as it is the recommended technique when studying the entire population. Data for the study are extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies across various years. Model estimation involves utilizing both the pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Random Effects Regression methods following additional diagnostic tests.

Table 1 Variable Measurement and Justification

Variable	Acronym	Type	Measurement	Justification
Corporate Social Responsibility Expenditure.	CSRE	Dependent	Total amount spent on social responsibility activities.	Shabirina and Cahyono (2023); Tan (2022); Ugbor <i>et al.</i> (2021).
Return on Assets	ROA	Independent	Profit after Tax dividend by Total Assets.	Shabirina and Cahyono (2023); Wardana <i>et al.</i> (2022);
Firm Leverage	FLEV	Independent	Debt-to-equity ratio (portion of Assets made up of debts).	Mudjiyanti <i>et al.</i> (2022); Ezejiyor and Emenaka (2022);
Inflation Rate	INFLR	Moderating	A rise in the prices of goods services.	Ichado <i>et al.</i> (2020); Ali and Ibrahim (2018()); Batsinda and Shukla (2016).

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2023.

This research utilized a bi-model specification approach due to the intricate connections, both direct and indirect, at play. The initial model encompasses the relationships among the independent variables, including the moderator, and the dependent variable. Meanwhile, the second model focuses on the indirect association between the independent variables and the dependent variable, moderated by inflation (the moderating variable)

The specified linear functional relationship equation for model I is:

$$CSRE = (ROA+LEV)$$

Econometrically, the above relation equation is shown as follows:

$$CSRE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2LEV_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots \text{Model I.}$$

The Model II specified linear functional relationship equation is written as:

$$CSRE = (ROA + LEV + INFLR*ROA + INFLR*LEV).$$

Expressing the above linear relationship equation in econometric terms, it becomes:

$$CSRE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2LEV_{it} + \beta_3INFLR*ROA_{it} + \beta_4INFLR*LEV_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \text{Model II.}$$

Where:

CSRE = a predictor for Corporate Social Responsibility Expenditure (Dependent variable);

ROA = a predictor for Return on Assets measuring profitability (a proxy for the independent variable);

LEV = a predictor for Leverage Ratio (a proxy for the independent variable);

β_0 = a constant and its coefficient;

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Coefficients of the proxies of the independent variables;

$\beta_3 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of the inflation-moderated proxies of the independent variables.

i = Firms;

t = Time;

μ = Error term; and

f = a functional relationship.

Results and Discussion

The data analysis was carried out with the aid of Descriptive statistics, Pearson multicollinearity test, Skewness/Kurtosis normality test, heteroskedasticity test and Hausman Specification test.

The regression analysis of the two models were done with Random robust regression.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 below describes the statistics of the variables of this study

VARIABLE	OBS	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX
L_CSRE	169	4.535	3.527	0	9.46
ROA	160	0.021	0.032	-0.08	0.242
LEV	160	0.880	0.723	0.094	0.965
INFLR	169	13.023	3.641	8	18.85

Source: STATA software output, 2023.

The descriptive statistics presented above indicate that only CSRE and INFLR have complete data for the entire period, consisting of 169 observations. This is attributed to the nature of inflation rates (INFLR), which are autonomously assigned values to variables. Additionally, CSRE recorded a value of zero in cases where no expenditures were incurred. For the years 2010-2018, BUA Cement Plc, listed in 2019, lacks data for ROA and LEV. Notably, CSRE exhibits a mean value of 4.535 and a standard deviation of 3.527. This lower standard deviation suggests that CSRE had a more concentrated distribution around its mean, indicating a relatively low growth rate. A minimum value of 0 implies that some companies either did not engage in socially responsible activities or failed to report them.

Examining ROA, it is observed to have a minimum of -0.08 and a maximum of 0.242. The standard deviation of 0.032 surpasses the mean value of 0.021, indicating a wider dispersion from the mean and suggesting a higher variability in ROA. As for LEV, its mean figure of 0.088 exceeds the standard deviation of 0.723, suggesting that LEV was less widely dispersed from the central mean. This implies a slower growth rate for LEV, with a minimum of 0.094 and a maximum of 0.965.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 3 displays the outcomes of the multicollinearity test, which was performed to assess the extent of relationships among the independent variables. The criterion for identifying multicollinearity (indicating a lack of independence) is when the correlation between a pair of independent variables exceeds 0.85. Conversely, the absence of multicollinearity is acknowledged when all pairs of independent variables exhibit correlations below 0.85.

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Using Pearson Correlation

	L_CSRE	ROA	LEV	INFL
L_CSRE	1.000			
ROA	0.063	1.000		
LEV	-0.059	0.069	1.000	
INFLR	0.040	0.248*	0.183	1.000
	0.610	0.0016	0.207	

Source: STATA software output, 2023.

Table 3 findings indicate that LEV exhibits a negative association with corporate social responsibility expenditure, displaying a coefficient of -0.059; however, this correlation is statistically insignificant at 0.456. Moreover, ROA demonstrates an inconsequential correlation coefficient of 0.063 with CSRE. Additionally, ROA exhibits insignificant positive correlations with LEV at 0.069 and a noteworthy positive relationship (0.002) with the inflation rate (INFLR) at 0.248. These outcomes suggest that none of the independent variables displays a correlation coefficient exceeding 0.85 with the others, implying the absence of multicollinearity issues in the models.

Normality Test

Table 4 illustrates the results of the normality test conducted using Skewness/Kurtosis statistical tools to ascertain the distribution pattern of residuals within the models. According to the decision rule, any model with a p-value less than or equal to 0.05 indicates residuals that are not normally distributed, while a p-value exceeding 0.05 suggests normally distributed residuals.

Table 4 Normality Test

Variable	Obs	----- joint ----- Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
residuals	160	0.0000	0.7138	14.33	0.0035

Source: STATA software, 2023.

The findings presented in Table 4 demonstrate a significant p-value of 0.0035 (significance level of 1%). This suggests, according to the decision rule, that, the residuals of the models deviate from a normal distribution. The presence of this abnormal residual distribution indicates a violation of a crucial assumption of the Ordinary Least Square regression method, namely normality. Consequently, the application of OLS regression techniques for estimating the model

is inappropriate. In light of this, Kutner *et al.* (2004) advocate the utilization of robust regression for this dataset, as it is not susceptible to the impact of abnormal residual distributions.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Table 5 displays the outcomes of the heteroskedasticity test conducted to assess the stability (consistency) of the residual variance within the model. The criterion for decision-making is to embrace the null hypothesis of constant variance when the p-value exceeds 0.05 or to reject the hypothesis when the p-value is equal to or less than 0.05.

Table 5 Heteroskedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
Chi2(1)	19.11
Prob > chi2	0.0000

Source: STATA 13 software output, 2023.

Table 5 revealed a p-value of 0.0000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis concerning constant variance according to the decision rule. This outcome indicates the presence of heteroskedasticity in the models, suggesting that a more suitable approach for estimation is robust regression. As per Fernandes *et al.* (2019), this method is less susceptible to distortions arising from data with atypical behaviour, such as non-constant (unstable) residual variance.

Hausman Specification Test

Table 6 Hausman Specification Test

Chi2 (5)	7.49
Prob>chi2	= 0.1865

Source: STATA software output, 2023.

Table 6 presents the results of the Hausman specification test, aiming to identify the more suitable method for estimating the specified models between random effects. The criteria for decision-making involve accepting the null hypothesis—asserting that differences in coefficients are not systematic—if the p-value exceeds 0.05. In such cases, a random effect estimator is utilized, which is inconsistent under the alternate hypothesis but efficient under the null hypothesis. Conversely, rejecting the null hypothesis is warranted if the p-value is equal to or less than 0.05, leading to the selection of a fixed effect estimator that maintains consistency under both null and alternate hypotheses. Table 6 shows a p-value of 0.1865 for the Hausman specification test. According to the decision rule, this result leads to the acceptance of the null

hypothesis, suggesting that differences in coefficients were not systematic. Consequently, the random effect estimation method is deemed preferable, leading to the adoption of random robust regression analysis for this study.

Model I Regression Analysis

Table 7 below reveals the results of the model I regression analysis conducted with the aid of Random Robust Regression. The results were used to test hypotheses i and ii.

Table 7 Model I Regression Analysis

L_CSRE	COEF.	ROBUST STD. ERR.	Z	P> Z
ROA	0.567	2.726	0.21	0.835
LEV	-0.295	0.022	-13.47	0.000***
INFLR	-0.116	0.046	-2.55	0.011
_cons	-0.935	1.508	0.62	0.429
R-squared overall				0.451
Wald chi ² (5)				480.47
Prob > chi ²				0.000 ***

Source: STATA software output, 2023.

Table 7 indicates that Model I exhibits an overall R-squared value of 0.451, signifying the coefficient of determination, commonly referred to as Goodness of Fit. This value of 0.451 suggests that the collective impact of the four independent variables: ROA, LEV, INFLR*ROA and INFLR*LEV accounts for approximately 45% of the variations in corporate social responsibility expenditure among the sampled industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2010 to 2022. Table 7 presented above demonstrates that there is an insignificant (0.835) positive (0.21) correlation between return on assets (ROA), a metric for profitability, and the corporate social responsibility expenditures of industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2010 to 2022. Consequently, the acceptance of null hypothesis one (H_{01}). These results suggest that, while holding other variables constant, a one-unit increase in profitability (ROA) corresponds to a 0.6 unit increase in corporate social responsibility expenditures. This outcome aligns with the findings of Shabirina and Cahyono (2023) and Mudjiyanti *et al.* (2022). The observed pattern supports the Stakeholders Theory, which advocates for corporations to contribute to society for the well-being of those impacted by their activities.

Moving on to Hypothesis Two, the same table reveals a noteworthy (0.000) negative (-13.47) association between the leverage ratio (LEV) and corporate social responsibility expenditures for industrial goods companies in Nigeria over the period 2010-2022, supported by a coefficient of -

0.295. This outcome leads to the rejection of null hypothesis two (H_{02}). This implies that with other variables held constant, a one-unit increase in the leverage ratio results in a decrease of approximately 0.295 units in corporate social responsibility expenditures. This finding aligns with the conclusions of Ezejiofor and Emeneka (2022) and Aimuyedo *et al.* (2022). The observed trend supports the Legitimacy Theory, which suggests that society should permit companies to generate profits before expecting them to engage in socially responsible initiatives.

Model II Regression Analysis

Table 8 shows the results of the regression analysis for model II conducted with the use of Random Robust Regression techniques. The results were used for testing hypotheses iii and iv.

Table 8 Model II Regression Analysis

L_CSRE	COEF.	ROBUST STD. ERR.	Z	P> Z
INFLR_ROA	-0.154	0.582	-0.26	0.792
INFLR_LEV	0.020	0.018	1.15	0.250
ROA	3.039	7.458	0.41	0.684
LEV	0.282	0.024	11.75	0.000
_cons	- 0.692	0.487	-1.42	0.176
R-squared overall				0.466
Wald chi ² (7)				409.28
Prob > chi ²				0.000***

Source: STATA software output, 2023.

Table 8 discloses that the model exhibits an overall R-squared value of 0.466, signifying the coefficient of determination, commonly known as Goodness of Fit. This 0.466 value implies that around 47% of the variations in the dependent variable, corporate social responsibility expenditures over the thirteen years (2010-2012), are jointly determined by the inflation-moderated variables and the variables ROA, LEV, and their free states. Additionally, Table 8 demonstrates that the model possesses a Wald chi2 of 409.28 with a prob> chi2 of 0.000, indicating a well-fitted model and suggesting that the outcomes are not merely coincidental. According to Table 8, the association between return on assets (ROA) and corporate social responsibility expenditures of Nigerian quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2010-2022, moderated by inflation rate (INFLR*ROA), is statistically insignificant (0.792) and exhibits a negligible negative relationship (-0.26), as indicated by the coefficient of -0.154. This result leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis three (H_{03}). These findings suggest that, under constant conditions for all other variables, a one-unit rise in inflation will adversely impact the relationship between profitability and corporate social responsibility by 0.15 units.

Table 8 findings reveal that the relationship between leverage ratio (LEV) and corporate social responsibility expenditures of Nigerian quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2010-2022, moderated by inflation rates (INFLR*LEV), is statistically insignificant (0.250) and demonstrates a minimal positive association (1.15), with a coefficient of 0.020. Consequently, null hypothesis four (H_{04}) is accepted. These results indicate that, under conditions where all other variables remain constant, a one-unit increase in inflation will enhance the connection between the leverage ratio and corporate social responsibility by 0.020 units.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's findings lead to the following conclusions: a) Ensuring higher profitability is crucial for prompting increased socially responsible activities among Nigerian industrial goods companies. This is because it positively influences Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), even if the impact is seemingly insignificant. b) A heightened leverage ratio acts as a deterrent to socially responsible activities within these companies. This is due to the financial burden of borrowing costs, leaving limited funds for social initiatives, as the leverage ratio demonstrates a significant negative correlation with Corporate Social Responsibility Expenditure (CSRE). c) In the relationship between profitability and CSR activities among Nigerian industrial goods companies, inflation rates play a relatively weak moderating role. Their insignificant negative moderating effect suggests that inflation rates do not strongly influence this relationship. d) In moderating the impact of the leverage ratio on corporate social responsibility, inflation rates prove ineffective, exhibiting an insignificant yet positive effect on the relationship between these variables.

The study proposes the following recommendations:

i) Management of Nigerian industrial goods companies should prioritize maximizing profits, as this empowers them to implement more impactful socially responsible programs; ii) Discouraging an increase in the leverage ratio is advisable if addressing societal needs is a top priority. This is because the payment of interest on borrowed capital significantly diminishes earnings, making it challenging, if not impossible, for heavily indebted companies to respond to social needs.; iii) When analyzing the impact of a third variable on the relationship between profitability and corporate social responsibility, the inflation rate is not a substantial factor, as it only insignificantly moderates the relationship; iv) In scenarios where the influence of another

variable is crucial to the relationship between the leverage ratio and corporate social responsibility, inflation rates should not be a consideration.

REFERENCES

- Adam, H. (2020). Leverage. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/l/leverage.asp>
- Adediran, S. A., Adejoh, E., & Oyewole, O. S. (2019). Effect of firms' characteristics on the timeliness of financial reports of quoted insurance companies in Nigeria, *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(24), 47- 58.
- Aimuyedo, M. T., Nyor, T., Agbi, S. E., & Ahmed, M. N. (2022). Leverage and sustainability reporting: Moderating roles of firm size of Nigerian industrial goods companies. *International Journal of Contemporary Accounting Issues-IJCAI (formerly International Journal of Accounting and Finance (IJAF))*, 11(2), 1-24.
- Akubo, D., Ekpa, F., Ochepe, A. A., Ochidi, Z., & Elaigwu, B. E. (2018). Impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Lapai International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 10(1&2), 301-314.
- Al-Akayleh, W., & Saaydah, M. (2022). Determinants of corporate social responsibility disclosure: An empirical study of Jordanian firms listed on Amman Stock Exchange. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 26(2), 1-18.
- Ali, M., & Ibrahim, P. (2018). Inflation and companies' performance: cross-sectional analysis- *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nano-Science*. <http://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2018.11694>.
- Aliyu, O. H., Abdullahi, S. R., & Adediran, S. A. (2021). Effect of board characteristics on sustainability reporting of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Leadership, Accounting Development and Investigation Research (JLADIR)*, 5(1), 20-35.
- Astuti, D. W. (2019). Profitabilitas, Leverage, dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Luas Pengungkapan Tanggung Jawab Sosial Perusahaan Pertambangan Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia (BEI) Periode 2013-2018. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dewantara Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Sarjanawiyata Tamansiswa*.

- Audu, U. A., Audu, F., Ude, A. O., & Adediran, S. A. (2022). Relationship between corporate social responsibility, financial performance and firm value: A study of multinational companies. *Journal of Leadership, Accounting Development and Investigation Research*, 6(1), 163-173. <https://doi.org/10.54164/LC.J.2022.7>.
- Badjuri, A. (2011). Faktor-faktor Fundamental, Mekanisme Corporate Governance, Pengungkapan Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Perusahaan Manufaktur dan Sumber Daya Alam Di Indonesia. *Dinamika Keuangan dan Perbankan*. 3(1), 38-54.
- Batsinda, G., & Shukla, J. (2019). Inflation and profitability of commercial banks in Rwanda: A case study of Bank of Kigali. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 14, 35-47. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v14n10p35>.
- behaviour. *Pacific Sociological Review*, 18, 122-136. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1388226>.
- Cui, W. (2020). Is debt conservatism the solution to financial constraints? An empirical analysis of Japanese firms. *Applied Economics* 52(23), 2526-2543.
- Dowling, J., & Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational legitimacy: social values and organizational
- Edicha, M. J., Abdullahi, S. R., & Ude, A. O. (2021). Dividend policy and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The moderating effect of firm age. *Journal of Leadership, Accounting Development and Investigation Research*, 5(1), 129-141.
- Ekpa, F., Ereh, J., & Edicha, M. J. (2019). Effect of firm characteristics on timeliness of financial reporting of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *KSU Research Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 2(2), 72-83.
- EU Commission, (2002). *Corporate social responsibility: A business contribution to Sustainable Development*. http://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2006/february/tradoc_127374.pdf.
- Ezejiofor, R. A., & Emeneka, O. L. (2022). Leverage and social sustainability reporting on listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 8(3), 1-14.
- Fernandes, A. A. R., Hutahayan, B., Solimun, A. E., Yanti, I., Astuti, A.B., Nurjannah, A., & Amaliana, L. (2019). *Comparison of curve estimation of the smoothing spline nonparametric function path based on PLS and PWLS in various levels of heteroscedasticity*. IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, Forthcoming Issue.

- Financial Reporting Council (FRC) (2018). *Code of corporate governance*.
- Hausman, J. A. (1978), Specification tests in econometrics. *Econometrica*, 46(1), 1251-1271.
- Ibrahim, A., Ude, A. O., & Adediran, S. A. (2020). Effect of working capital management on profitability of quoted foods and beverages companies in Nigeria: Firm size as a moderator. *Journal of Leadership, Accounting Development and Investigation Research*, 4(1), 33-43.
- Ichado, I. A., Audu, F., & Wada, J. (2020). Moderating role of inflation on the impact of budgetary allocation on poverty reduction in Nigeria. *Journal of Leadership, Accounting Development and Investigation Research*, 4(1), 69-78.
- Kennedy, D. A. (2008). Reflections on mediation. *Organizational Research Methods*, 11(1), 353-358.
- Kogan, L., & Tian, M. (2012). *Firm characteristics and empirical factor models: A data-mining experiment*. International Finance Discussion papers, 1070.
- Kutner, M. H., Nachtsheim, C. J., & Neter, J. (2004). *Applied linear statistical model*. McGraw-Hill.
- Lai, Y. H. (2013). The moderating effect of organizational structure in knowledge management for international ports in Taiwan. *International Journal of Computer and Information Technology*, 2(2), 240-246.
- Mukhtaruddin, M., Saftiana, Y., & Dwikatama, P. A. (2018). Firm's characteristics, corporate governance quality and corporate social responsibility disclosure. *SRIWIJAYA International Journal of Dynamic Economics and Business*, 2(3), 193-212. <http://ejournal.unsri.ac.id/index.php/sijdeb>.
- Nigerian Exchange Group (NDX: 2022). Delisted companies.
- Ohonba, N., & I. E. Ogbeide. (2021). Firm structure and corporate social responsibility disclosures in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 5(2), 62-78.
- Rohmadini, A., M., Saifi, D. A., & Darmawan, A. (2018). Pengaruh profitabilitas, likuiditas dan leverage terhadap financial distress (studi pada perusahaan food & beverage Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia periode 2013-2016). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 61(2), 11-19.

- Santioso, L., & Chandra, E. (2012). Corporate social responsibility (influence of profitability, company size, leverage, age of company, and independent board of commissioners in disclosure of corporate social responsibility). *Jurnal Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 14(1), 1-12.
- Santosa, T. R., & Budiasih, G. A. N. (2021). The effect of profitability, leverage and liquidity on corporate social responsibility disclosures: A study on food and beverage sub-sector of the manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (2017-2019). *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 5(4), 372-379.
- Shabirina, A. T., & Cahyono, Y. T. (2023). The effect of firm size, profitability, liquidity, leverage, and public ownership on corporate social responsibility disclosure. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(4), 31-39.
- Shuaibu, K. (2020). Firm characteristics and environmental disclosure quality of listed cement companies in Nigeria. *African Scholar Journal of Management. Science and Entrepreneurship*, 18(7), 105-118.
- Swandari, F., & Sadikin, A. (2016). The effect of ownership structure, profitability, leverage, and firm size on corporate social responsibility (CSR). *Binus Business Review* 7(3), 315-320.
- Tan, W. (2022). Effect of financial performance, firm size, and leverage on corporate social responsibility: Empirical study on mining companies listed on the Indonesia stock exchange. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 5(3), 20048-20055.
- Ugbor, R. O., Inyama, O. I., Omodero, C. O., & Inyama, E.C. (2021). Enterprise financial characteristics and corporate social responsibility costs of oil and gas businesses in Nigeria *Journal of Legal Studies*, 28(42), 142-162. [hps://doi.org/10.2478/jles-2021-0016](https://doi.org/10.2478/jles-2021-0016).
- Valipour, H., Moradi, J., & Farsi, F. D. (2012). The impact of company characteristics on working
- Wardana, T., Nugroho, M., Rahmiyati, N., Mahasiswa, D. P., & Dosen Pembimbing, D. (2022). The effect of profitability, liquidity, and company size on firm value through corporate social responsibility in LQ45 companies listed on the Indonesia stock exchange. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Science*, 6(2), 37-39.
- Yuliana, R., Mambang, P., & Eko, G. S. (2008). Corporate social responsibility and the investor. *Journal of Accounting*, 5(2), 245-276.

- Zaman, Q. U., Ehsan, S., Hassan, M. K., Javed, M., & Hassan, S. I. U. (2023). Corporate social responsibility and zero leverage. *Jurnal Ekonomi Malaysia* 56(1), 33-46. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17576/JEM-2022-5601-03>.
- Zayol, P. I., Akpa, A., Tsegba, I. N., & Gberindyer A. C. (2022). Firm characteristics and corporate environmental disclosure by the less-sensitive listed companies in Nigeria. *AE-FUNAI Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance (FJABAF)*, 8(1), 14-34.